

Toolkit walkthrough

a HOW TO guide for GENTE toolkit users

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Contents

of the GENTE Toolkit walkthrough

- 1 What is it & Who is it for
- 2 Overview of format & Methodology used to create it
- 3 Stages & Topics & Sections within the toolkit
- 4 Use case examples of how the toolkit can be used & the types of information included
- 5 Availability - where the toolkit can be accessed

GENTE Toolkit

What is it

Connects together all the **outcomes, learnings, tools, services, and research** of the GENTE project.

Provides access to outcomes in a **user-friendly way**, directing users to relevant information quickly.

Who is it for

Anyone interested in **joining, setting up, participating** in, and/or **operating** a local energy community.

GENTE Toolkit

Who developed it

Research partners

Industry partners

Community partners

What is the source of the content

The content of the toolkit is made up of the reports, deliverables, code, data, test case results, and published academic papers that the GENTE project produced.

GENTE Toolkit - Stages

GENTE Energy Community Toolkit

MOTIVATION	CREATION	OPERATION	INSPIRATION
Why should I participate in an energy community?	How do I setup and/or participate in an energy community?	What technology and tools are available to operate an energy community?	What energy communities exist already and how do they operate?
Purpose	Goals & Motivations	Why	People
Why are energy communities an important concept?	Who are the relevant stakeholders and what is their role?	What use cases exist for the creation and operation of energy communities?	How many energy communities are there in Europe?
How do we make decisions?	What types of energy community business model are there and how are they defined?	How do the different aspects of a building (materials, type of controller, outdoor conditions, occupancy) affect building energy performance and indoor conditions?	Can and/or should energy (E) be forecast for the subject building?
What can I do to improve the energy production from the PV solar panels on my roof?	How can the energy production and consumption of an energy community be optimized?	What is a common example of conceptual data needs for energy communities?	Where can I find information and guidance about other energy community topics?

Each Stage is divided into **Topics** to give **structure** to the content.

The screenshot displays the GENTE Energy Community Toolkit interface, which is organized into several stages and topics. The main content area is divided into four primary stages: MOTIVATION, CREATION, OPERATION, and INSPIRATION. Each stage is further divided into specific topics, such as 'Future energy community scenarios', 'Energy community definition', 'Technical & privacy perspective', 'Grid support services', and 'Building Energy Management System'. The interface includes a navigation menu on the left with sections like 'KEY TERMS', 'RESOURCES', and 'Energy community definition'. The right side of the interface features a 'Tools' section with various resources and a 'Resources' section with links to external documents and reports. The overall layout is clean and user-friendly, with a focus on providing comprehensive information and guidance for energy communities.

GENTE Toolkit - Topics

MOTIVATION

Why should I participate in or setup an energy community?

Purpose

Why

People

Use cases

Goals & Motivations

Future of energy communities

what energy communities are for
what they do
what goals they can help fulfil
the stakeholders involved
what type of cases they can be applied to
how they might contribute in the future to
the energy transition

GENTE Toolkit - Topics

CREATION

How do I setup and/or participate in an energy community?

Process

Options

the process involved in creating a new community

what options exist for the setup of a new community, such as business models, organisational models, regulations that exist in your locality, etc

GENTE Toolkit - Topics

OPERATION

What technology and tools are available to operate an energy community?

Simulate

Manage

Forecast

Optimize

how energy communities can be simulated to help define the optimal setup and operation

how production and consumption can be forecast in various ways

tools for managing energy communities

methods for optimising the operation of communities to maximise on achieving the goals of the community

GENTE Toolkit - Topics

INSPIRATION

What energy communities exist already and how do they operate?

GENTE demo sites

Other toolkits

the GENTE demo sites
toolkits created by other projects to
provide more extensive / broader set of
information than just GENTE can
provide

GENTE Toolkit - Sections

QUESTIONS YOU MIGHT BE ASKING

Identify Stages that will help answer your specific questions

Provides insight into the types of questions the content of the toolkit aims to answer

KEY TERMS

Identify Stages that relate to particular topics you are interested in

Used to aid in searching for content in topic areas of interest

RESOURCES

Links to relevant information, reports, findings, outcomes, results of test cases & KPIs, videos, code, data, and articles developed in GENTE for each Stage

Toolkit Use Cases

Explain how the toolkit can be used & types of information included

- 1 Forecast
- 2 Co-design
- 3 Optimize
- 4 Example of energy communities

GENTE Energy Community Toolkit

MOTIVATION	CREATION	OPERATION	Manage	Optimize	INSPIRATION
<p>Why should participants in an energy community?</p> <p>What is an energy community?</p> <p>How can we use energy communities?</p> <p>What are the main challenges?</p> <p>What are the main benefits?</p> <p>What are the main risks?</p> <p>What are the main opportunities?</p>	<p>How do I set up an energy community?</p>	<p>What technology and tools are available to operate an energy community?</p> <p>How can I use the toolkit?</p>	<p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p> <p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p> <p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p> <p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p> <p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p>	<p>How can I optimize energy production?</p>	<p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p>
<p>What is an energy community?</p> <p>How can we use energy communities?</p> <p>What are the main challenges?</p> <p>What are the main benefits?</p> <p>What are the main risks?</p> <p>What are the main opportunities?</p>	<p>How do I set up an energy community?</p>	<p>What technology and tools are available to operate an energy community?</p> <p>How can I use the toolkit?</p>	<p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p> <p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p> <p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p> <p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p> <p>How can I improve the energy production from my solar panels?</p>	<p>How can I optimize energy production?</p>	<p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p>

This use case shows entry points for a user's area of interest that exists as a specific top-level **Topic** in the toolkit.

Use the **Topics** in each **Stage** to navigate to desired information.

Simulate

- How do different aspects of a building (materials, location, outdoor conditions, occupancy) affect building performance and energy consumption?
- How can I simulate building energy consumption using the energy model?
- How can I simulate building energy consumption using the energy model?
- How can I simulate building energy consumption using the energy model?

Forecast

- How can I forecast energy generation (e.g. PV output) using the energy model?
- How can I forecast energy generation (e.g. PV output) using the energy model?
- How can I forecast energy generation (e.g. PV output) using the energy model?
- How can I forecast energy generation (e.g. PV output) using the energy model?

Manage

- How can I manage energy production from my solar panels?
- How can I manage energy production from my solar panels?
- How can I manage energy production from my solar panels?
- How can I manage energy production from my solar panels?

Optimize

- How can I optimize energy production?

INSPIRATION

- What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?
- What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?
- What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?
- What is some example of conceptual data models for energy communities?

Co-design process

- Co-design process
- Co-design process
- Co-design process
- Co-design process

Use case definition

- Use case definition
- Use case definition
- Use case definition
- Use case definition

Technical & privacy perspective

- Technical & privacy perspective

GENTE Toolkit - Use case: Forecast

GENTE Toolkit - Use case: Co-design

GENTE Toolkit - Use case: Co-design

Searching the toolkit will direct you to the Stages that contain content for that topic.

From there, **navigating** to the the Resources section provides links to relevant GENTE content.

Clicking on the links will open the content, in this case, a summary of how a part of the co-design process was implemented in the GENTE project in the creation of a potential new energy community.

How can end users and other stakeholders be involved in the

GENTE Energy Community Toolkit

MOTIVATION Why should participants in an energy community?	CREATION How do I help and/or participate in an energy community?	OPERATION What technology and tools are available to operate an energy community?	INSPIRATION What energy communities exist already and how do they operate?
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This use case provides examples of the **different forms of content** that are included in the toolkit.

Simulate	Forecast	Manage	Optimize	GENTE demo sites	Other toolkits
<ul style="list-style-type: none">How do different aspects of a building (materials, type of glazing, outdoor conditions, occupancy) affect building performance and energy consumption?Are the benefits of combining building and energy systems during the design process?How can we better optimize a building's energy system?How can we better forecast support efficient operation of district heating systems or heat pumps?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Can and/or how often (if not) be forecast (on the output side)?How can renewable energy generation (e.g. PV output) be forecast (on the input side) to optimize the grid?What is the most reliable way to forecast electricity demand and supply for efficient energy balance?How can best load forecasting support efficient operation of district heating systems or heat pumps?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">What can be done to improve the energy production from the PV solar panels?What is the overall performance level of the PV modules and why are they underperforming?How to schedule devices within a building to minimize cost and peak load?How to handle uncertainties related to PV and load forecast?How much flexibility can be provided by buildings?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">How can the energy production and consumption of an energy community be optimized?What tools exist to optimize energy production?What tools exist to optimize energy consumption?What goals and/or services can energy communities be optimized to fulfil?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">What are some examples of conceptual data models for energy communities?What are some examples of typical data models for energy communities?What are some examples of data management systems used to store and/or analyze energy community data?What is the potential for energy communities in reducing CO2 emissions?Can an energy community help me increase autonomy and self-consumption of my PV installation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Where can I find information and guidance about other energy community use cases?What other tools and guidance exist to help me design and operate an energy community?
Digital twin	Generation forecasting	Building Energy Management System	Optimizer	Am Aawasser - Switzerland	Toolkits from other projects
<ul style="list-style-type: none">DL3 report - "Future energy community scenarios"DL3 report - "Future energy community scenarios"DL3 report - "Future energy community scenarios"Research paper - based on DL3 - "The Development of Energy Communities in Europe: Policy Success Factors, Future Prospects"	<ul style="list-style-type: none">DL2 report - "Edge-based DL3 forecasting and algorithmic algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL3 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL4 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL5 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"	<ul style="list-style-type: none">DL2 report - "Advanced BEMS for Building Control as a Service"Research paper - "A Novel Energy Management System for Optimal Energy and Building Scheduling of Residential Buildings: A Case Study in a Real Estate"Research paper - "Energy prediction from solar and PV using a neural network"DL3 report - "Edge-based DL3 forecasting and algorithmic algorithm, including energy forecasting results"Article - "CoCoach at Am Aawasser"	<ul style="list-style-type: none">DL3 report - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm"Blog post - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm"DL4 report - "Optimize algorithm, control, and scheduling"	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Am Aawasser websiteAm Aawasser websiteArticle - "Forecast of Am Aawasser"Video - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm"Blog post - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm"DL1 - Presentation & Documentation - Software for energy storageDL2 report - "Edge-based DL3 forecasting and algorithmic algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL3 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL4 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL5 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL6 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL7 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL8 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL9 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL10 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL11 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL12 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL13 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL14 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL15 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL16 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL17 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL18 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL19 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL20 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"	<ul style="list-style-type: none">DL3 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL4 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL5 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL6 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL7 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL8 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL9 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL10 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL11 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL12 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL13 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL14 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL15 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL16 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL17 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL18 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL19 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL20 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"
Co-design process	Use case definition	Technical & privacy perspective	Grid support services	HSB Living Lab - Sweden	Energy community definition
<ul style="list-style-type: none">DL3 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL4 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL5 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL6 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL7 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL8 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL9 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL10 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL11 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL12 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL13 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL14 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL15 report - "Forecasting algorithm, including energy forecasting results"DL16 report - 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GENTE Toolkit - Use case: Optimize

 OPERATION
 What technology and tools are available to operate an energy community?

Optimize

How can the energy production and consumption of an energy community be optimized?

What tools exist to optimize energy production?

What tools exist to optimize energy consumption?

What goals and/or services can energy communities be optimised to fulfil?

Production estimates Heat pump optimization

Privacy-Preserving Learning Edge intelligence

Optimization Artificial intelligence (AI)

Uncertainty handling Flexibility

Self-consumption Autarky

Optimizer

- Video - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm" [Link](#)
- Blog post - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm" [Link](#)
- GitHub repo - Optimizer algorithm - control flexibilities [Link](#)

Generation forecasting

- D5.2 report - "Edge-based DER forecasting and diagnostic algorithm, including privacy-preserving learning" [Link](#)
- GitHub repo - Forecaster algorithm - forecast PV generation and electricity usage [Link](#)
- GitHub repo - Jupyter notebook of forecasting results [Link](#)
- D6.1 report - "Advanced Load and Generation Forecast" [Link](#)
- Research paper - "Scalable and Lightweight Machine Learning Based Load Forecast: Netload versus Disaggregated Forecast" [Link](#)

The 'Optimize' Topic contains examples of all the **types of content** the toolkit includes, such as:

- Videos
- Blog posts & Articles
- Code & data repositories
- Reports
- Research papers

GENTE Toolkit - Use case: Optimize

Optimizer

- Video - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm"
- Blog post - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm"
- GitHub repo - Optimizer algorithm - control flexibilities

Generation forecasting

- D5.2 report - "Edge-based DER forecasting and diagnostic algorithm, including privacy-preserving learning"
- GitHub repo - Forecaster algorithm - forecast PV generation and electricity usage
- GitHub repo - Jupyter notebook of forecasting results
- D6.1 report - "Advanced Load and Generation Forecast"
- Research paper - "Scalable and Lightweight Machine Learning Based Load Forecast: Netload versus Disaggregated Forecast"

The **GENTE** Project
The **GENTE** Project is an international cooperation of:

- ES SYSTEMS
- CHALMERS UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
- ALINGRIS ENERGI
- PROSUME
- reengen ENERGY PLATFORM
- HSLU Hochschule Luzern

Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm

gente-hslu-outputs

Overview Repositories 4 Projects Packages Teams

All repositories

4 repositories

- forecasting Public
PV and electricity usage forecasting algorithm
Jupyter Notebook • 0 stars • 0 forks • 0 packages • Updated last week
- optimization Public
optimization algorithm to control flexibilities
Jupyter Notebook • 0 stars • 0 forks • 0 packages • Updated 2 weeks ago
- automated-was-search Private
- d52-edgeforecasting Private
Python • 0 stars • 0 forks • 0 packages • Updated 2 weeks ago

GENTE The Project News & Events Community Toolkit Resources Contact English

Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm

Published May 29, 2024

Controlling Data Acquisition LEC

EDGE-BASED DER FORECASTING AND DIAGNOSTIC ALGORITHM

Deliverable 5.2

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Scalable and Lightweight Machine Learning Based Load Forecast: Netload versus Disaggregated Forecast

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Abstract— This paper develops lightweight and adaptive demand forecast models for a residential building integrated with solar photovoltaics using scalable and adaptive deep learning algorithms, i.e., long short-term memory (LSTM) and gated recurrent units (GRU). First, the forecast models have been trained using the real measurement data from a residential building. Then, the models have been used in case studies using the real-time data for two forecasting approaches: 1) method forecast, 2) disaggregated forecast, i.e., forecasting the load and PV generation separately. The performance of the two forecasting approaches have been compared. The results from case studies showed that disaggregated forecast approach was superior (with an overall RMSE of 2.80 kW for the building with max demand of 1053 kW) than its aggregated forecast approach (with an overall RMSE of 2.63 kW). Case studies results have also demonstrated that the models are scalable with more data, and are lightweight, hence, suitable for resource-constrained devices. Although LSTM shows advantages in accuracy, GRU shows better scalability in terms of computational efficiency. The models can be utilized by various stakeholders, such as building owners, grid operators, etc., and can be adapted to other types of buildings.

Keywords— forecasting, method, lightweight, scalability, neural networks, deep learning, energy optimization

1. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and Motivation

Demand forecasting for buildings is becoming one of the important elements in the energy management system of buildings. It is more so when more renewable energy sources (e.g., solar photovoltaics - PV), new types of loads such as heat-pumps, battery energy storages, electric vehicles, etc., are being integrated to buildings. Accurate load forecasts could lead to a reduction in both operational and maintenance costs for buildings. From the end-user's perspective, reliable forecasts will help in daily energy management and scheduling with potential cost and energy saving. Therefore, there is a need to develop advanced demand forecast model in such way that potential high volatility and uncertainty associated with energy loads and building integrated PVs could be addressed. Forecasting of load demand in PVs integrated buildings can be done by forecasting the netload or by forecasting load demand and PV production separately. The main question here is which approach would be better and in which conditions.

B. Related Work

Efforts have been made in load forecasting but not much in the direction of method. Several forecasting strategies exist

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SUMMARY

This deliverable introduces an edge intelligence application aimed at forecasting the future production of solar panel installations by leveraging available data sources, including historical solar panel output and meteorological predictions. The objective of the AI-based model is to estimate the future power production of a PV array within a relatively short time frame (1 day) by utilizing past meteorological data and forecasts.

Fig. 1. Representation of a building's load and generation

Recognizing the importance of individual electric users in grid planning and operation, [2] carried out a user level load forecasting to analyze integrated energy system influential factors and proposed a new user level load forecast method. [3] made a short-term individual household forecast and added up the resulting values as aggregated users in a large-scale prediction. [4] used data-driven approach to decompose the netload for easy modeling and forecasting. A blend of these forecast strategies is implemented in [5], focusing on both single household and low aggregate levels loads.

1) Individual component forecasting

This approach implies forecasting method indirectly, that is, forecasting PV production and electric load individually, then subtract the PV forecast from the electric load forecast. Achieving such a forecast requires a time series of PV production, electricity and netload, complemented with certain explanatory variables, such as weather. However, the stochastic nature and high uncertainty associated with these variables, makes it difficult for accurate prediction, especially for PV production [6]. In addition, calendar variables, such as the day type (weekday or weekend), hour of the day, and season of the year and temperature, consumption behavior by the consumers, etc., have strong influence on electricity load forecast.

Several forecasting techniques, such as in [7-9], had been deployed in electric load forecasting, covering processes of problem formulation, data transformation to supervised learning, and feature learning. Short-term forecasting strategy to learn residents' consumption behavior has been introduced in [10, 11], while [12, 13] predicted a building best load using

GENTE Energy Community Toolkit

MOTIVATION	CREATION	OPERATION	OPERATION				INSPIRATION	
Why should I participate in an energy community?	How do I set up and participate in an energy community?	What technology and tools are available to operate an energy community?	Simulate	Forecast	Manage	Optimize	GENTE demo sites	Other toolkits
<p>What is an energy community?</p> <p>How can I set up an energy community?</p> <p>What are the main challenges?</p> <p>What are the benefits?</p> <p>What are the key success factors?</p>	<p>How do I set up and participate in an energy community?</p> <p>What are the main challenges?</p> <p>What are the benefits?</p> <p>What are the key success factors?</p>	<p>What technology and tools are available to operate an energy community?</p> <p>What are the main challenges?</p> <p>What are the benefits?</p> <p>What are the key success factors?</p>	<p>How do I simulate different aspects of a building, including solar panels, outdoor conditions, occupancy, etc.?</p> <p>How can I simulate building energy consumption during the design process?</p> <p>How can I simulate a heat pump system in a building?</p>	<p>How can I forecast energy generation (e.g. PV output) or consumption (e.g. electricity demand) in a building?</p> <p>How can I forecast electricity demand and supply for a building?</p> <p>How can I forecast the operation of a building system (e.g. heat pump)?</p>	<p>How can I manage energy production from a PV system?</p> <p>How can I manage energy consumption in a building?</p> <p>How can I manage energy storage?</p>	<p>How can I optimize energy production?</p> <p>How can I optimize energy consumption?</p> <p>How can I optimize energy storage?</p>	<p>What are some examples of conceptual data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What are some examples of input data models for energy communities?</p> <p>What are some examples of data management systems used to store energy community data?</p> <p>What is the potential for energy communities in reducing CO2 emissions?</p> <p>Can an energy community help me reduce costs and self-consumption of my PV system?</p>	<p>What are some other toolkits and guides available for energy communities?</p> <p>What are some other toolkits and guides available for energy communities?</p>
<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>	<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>	<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>	<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>	<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>	<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>	<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>	<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>	<p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p> <p>Energy Community Toolkit</p>

This use case shows entry routes to find information **about real-life energy communities**, mainly the GENTE demo sites.

GENTE Toolkit - Use case: Examples

Use the **search function** in Mural or your PDF viewer to find where your **search term** occurs in the toolkit.

GENTE Toolkit - Use case: Examples

The term *'example'* leads you to the extensive resources gathered throughout the project about the **GENTE demo sites.**

Find ✕

4 results < > Clear

✕

INSPIRATION

What energy communities exist already and how do they operate?

GENTE demo sites

- What are some examples of conceptual data models for LECs?
- What are some examples of logical data models for LECs?
- What are some examples of a data management system applied to real-world LECs (physical data models)?
- What is the potential for energy communities in reducing CO2 emissions?
- Could an energy community help me increase autarky and self consumption of my PV installation?
- Can energy communities help to reduce power peaks from the grid?

- Am Aawasser - Switzerland
- [Am Aawasser website](#)
 - [Am Aawasser Factsheet](#)
 - [Article - EcoCoach at Am Aawasser](#)
 - [Video - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm"](#)
 - [Blog post - "Introducing GENTE's Local Energy Community Optimization Algorithm"](#)
 - [D5.1 - Presentation & Documentation - SmartHelo sub-metering devices](#)
 - [D8.1 report - "GENTE System Architecture: Conceptual, logical and physical data models for LEC"](#)
 - [D9.1 report - "Test cases, assessment framework and KPIs"](#)
 - [Results - D9.2 report - "Summary of demo case requirements, scenarios, solutions and evaluation for each site"](#)
 - [GitHub repo - Am Aawasser Test Case results](#)
 - [Results - D9.3 report - "Assessment of demonstration, identification and lessons learned/best practices for replication"](#)

- HSB Living Lab - Sweden
- [HSB Living Lab website](#)
 - [HSB Living Lab Factsheet](#)
 - [D6.2 report - "Advanced BEMS for "Building control as a service"](#)
 - [Research paper - "A Novel Energy Management System for Optimal Energy and Flexibility Scheduling of Residential Buildings: A Case Study in HSB Living Lab"](#)
 - [Research paper - "Flexibility provision from battery storage and PV inverters using IoT platform: Real-life demonstrations at Chalmers campus"](#)
 - [D6.3 report - "Optimal LEC operation based on smart BEMS"](#)
 - [D6.4 report - "Grid support services from LEC to system operators"](#)
 - [D8.1 report - "GENTE System Architecture: Conceptual, logical and physical data models for LEC"](#)
 - [D9.1 report - "Test cases, assessment framework and KPIs"](#)
 - [D5.3 report abstract - "Community digital twin"](#)
 - [D5.3 report - "Community digital twin"](#)
 - [Research paper - based on D5.3](#)
 - [Results - D9.2 report - "Summary of demo case requirements, scenarios, solutions and evaluation for each site"](#)
 - [Results - D9.3 report - "Assessment of demonstration, identification and lessons learned/best practices for replication"](#)

Toolkit Availability

Where the toolkit can be accessed

- 1 On the GENTE website
<https://genteproject.com/community-toolkit/>
- 2 As a Mural board - [GENTE toolkit](#)
- 3 As PDFs - [Toolkit PDFs folder](#)

- Get in touch with the GENTE team via hello@genteproject.com

- Recommended citation for this guide:

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